

**ABOUT FERUZ'S GHAZALS THAT WERE NOT INCLUDED IN THE
EDITIONS (IN THE EXAMPLE MAJMUAT USH-SHUAROYI PAYRAVI
FERUZSHOHIIY)**

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Abstract The collection of poems “Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy” is known to contain tatabbu' gazals to the ghazals of the poets who worked in the literary environment in Khorezm at the end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century. The mentioned collection is kept in the main fund of Abu Rayhon Beruniy Oriental Studies Institute of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan under the number 1152, which provides valuable information about the era. The article also includes the realization of the plan for publishing the ghazals of Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz II.

The plan for publishing the ghazals of Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz II has been realized in the article. One hundred poems of the poet from the 1152nd collection have been compared with the publications “Ne bo'ldi yorim kelmadi” and “Elga shoh-u ishqqa qul” announced by G. Ismoilova in 1991 and 1994. It was noted that three of Feruz's ghazals mentioned in the collection did not appear in the publications, and some couplets of the ghazals were left out in the publications.

Key words: Feruz, collection, manuscript, publication, ghazal, poem.

Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz II played a significant role in the formation and development of the literary environment in Khorezm at the end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century. As a monarch, poet, and even a musician, Feruz elevated literature to a high level in Khorezm. Feruz supported and encouraged scholars, creating conditions for their creative work (Aminov, 2008; Muhammadiyeva, 2021; Qayumov, 1998; G'anixo'jayev, 1969; Jumaxo'ja, 1995,

1999; Qosimov, Yusupov, Dolimov, Rizayev, Ahmedov, 2004; Abdug‘afurov, 2003). Information about the literary figures of Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz's era can be found not only in the collections “Xiva shoir va adabiyotchilarining tarjimayi hollari” by Hasanmurod Laffasiy and “Xorazm shoir va navozandalari” by Bobojon Tarroh – Xodim, but also in other sources such as (Laffasiy, 1992; Xodim, 2011; Abdug‘afurov, 2005).

During that era, more than 30 poets, including Feruz, Tabibiy, Mutrib, Avaz, and Shinosiy, created works of poetry. They were mainly influenced by the works of prominent poets such as Navoiy, Ogahiy, Munis, and Ravnaq. Their successors followed their footsteps and demonstrated their talents in composition, imitation, and refinement. Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz II, a monarch and a poet, occupies a unique place in our literature due to his literary contributions. Studying his poems contained in manuscripts is one of the crucial issues of today's world.

The study of Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz's literary contributions began during his lifetime. In particular, various pieces of information about Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz's literary contributions can be found in works such as Ogahiy's “Shohid-ul Iqbol” (Shodmonov, 2009, p.33), Hasanmurod Laffasiy's “Tarjimayi hollari of Xiva Poets and Writers” (Laffasiy, 1992, pp.24-26), Bobojon Tarroh-Xodim's “Xorazm Poets and Musicians” (Xodim, pp.9-20), Ahmad Tabibiy's “Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy” (Tabibiy, inv. 1152, p.3b), and Bayoniy's “Shajarayi Xorazmshohiy” (Bayoniy, inv. 9596, p.200).

The first information about Feruz was given in Abdulla Qahhor's article “On Ashula” in 1960, before Uzbekistan gained independence. This article was written as a response to "the article of three authors" published in “Qizil O'zbekiston” newspaper. In it, Abdulla Qahhor criticized some classical poets for writing too many ashulas and the negative influence it had on some contemporary poets. Abdulla Qahhor mentions that some authors criticized Feruz for having too many wives, and advised him to obey the law and not to steal from the treasury or cause harm to others. Then, he poses the question, “Who is Feruz?” and goes on to

acknowledge him as a famous poet, musician, composer, and a skilled translator who bought a printing press in 1873 and published the first book in Khorezm. As such, Qahhor highly values Feruz's literary contributions and his character. (Qahhor, 1968, p.103).

The way to learn Feruz's creativity has expanded with the coming of the years of independence. In 1991, literary critic G. Ismoilova published a small book titled “Where has my sweetheart not come” that collected Feruz's poems. Subsequently, through further extensive research, a book of Feruz's poems titled “Serve nation and love” was announced in 1994 based on sources from the collections №12060, 3446 of the Oriental Institute at the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In 1995, the scholar defended her dissertation entitled “The literary environment of Feruz's era in Khorezm” due to the success of her research efforts.

In 1992, Polvonnazir Bobojonov prepared the book “Tazkirayi shuaro” under the occasion of the 2500th anniversary of the city of Khiva. This book includes information about Feruz and contains seven couplets of his ghazals with the reframe “paydo” and “mening”. Additionally, a single masnavi poem was also dedicated to Feruz by Laffasiy and included in the book (Bobojonov, 1992, pp. 24-26).

Furthermore, in 1991, the book “Feruz: king and poet's destiny” by Davlatyor Rahim and Shixnazar Matrasulov was published. The authors continued their scholarly research and in 2011, they published the book “Feruz” with new analysis and interpretations.

In 2021, Y. Muhammadiyeva defended her PhD dissertation on “The literary talent of Feruz” and successfully received her degree.

G. Ismoilova published Feruz's poems twice in 1991 and 1994, respectively. These works include "Ne bo'ldi yorim kelmadi" (52 ghazals) and “Serve nation and love” (98 ghazals, 4 masnavi poems, 6 (2 of which are takhmis) muhammads, 2 musaddas, and 7 rubaiyat). In her PhD dissertation on “The literary talent of Feruz”, Y. Muhammadiyeva reveals that the total volume of Feruz's literary heritage is 2534 verses, including 98 ghazals, 7 muhammads, 2 musaddas, 4 masnavi poems, and 7

rubaiyat, which aligns with the information provided in the previously mentioned publications (however, in this dissertation, it is mentioned that Feruz has written seven muhammads). According to Feruz's decree, a collection of his poems titled "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy" was compiled, and it was noted that the number of his ghazals was exactly 101. Currently, this collection is preserved in the main fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan under the number 1152. Initially, information about this collection was published in the second issue of "Abadiy meros" journal in 2nd edition "Tabibiy tuzgan ikki majmua haqida"gi maqolasida by F. Ganixojayev (Ganixojayev, 1971, pp. 211-219).

The book "Feruz: king and poet's destiny" by Davlatyor Rahim, Shixnazar Matrasulov, and Nusratullo Jumaxojalar also includes information about Tabibiy's collection of poems. The relevant details can be found on pages 24-25 of the book (Rahim, Matrasul, Jumaxojalar, 1995). In addition to this, S. Matkarimova provided comprehensive information on this topic in her doctoral dissertation on "Tabibiy tazkiranavis" in 2007 (Matkarimova, 2007). In her doctoral dissertation on "Murtib Xonaxarob and his literary heritage", S. Madirimova studied the Tabibiy's collection of poems from the perspective of literary criticism and text analysis. She wrote a scholarly monograph outlining her research and noted that thirty-two poets who were present in the royal court had written commendations on Feruz's one hundred and one ghazals (Madirimova, 2021, 26-27 pages).

Numerous literary studies have been conducted on the literary heritage of Feruz to date. However, his poems that are listed in the collected sources have not been studied in detail from a literary criticism and text analysis perspective yet. In this article, we compared Feruz II's ghazals from the collection "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy" compiled by Tabibiy with the ghazals published in 1991 and 1994 under the titles "Ne bo'ldi yorim kelmadi" and "Elga shoh-u ishqqa qul." Moreover, the 1152th collection contained only Feruz's ghazals and did not include other types of poems or literary works. It is essential to note that while the

information from previous sources is supplementary and corroborated Tabibiy's research, it has not been explicitly used in these modern studies. As a result, we found some differences between these sources: the attention-grabbing articles about the Tabibiy's collection were not presented in these previously mentioned publications:

1. *Missing couplets*

2. *Missing ghazals.*

1. When the compilation and publication were compared to each other, it was revealed that some ghazals and poems were left out during the publication. Specifically, a ghazal that starts with the line 'One night, a sweet melody came to my gathering, O heart' which consists of 9 couplets was reduced to 8 couplets in the publication. The verse that was excluded from the publication was moved to before the maqta in the collection. The specific verse is as follows:

Besabrliq aylab shior qilma havas busiy kanor

Qil ri'oyat diydorig'a har kun qanoat, ey ko'ngul.

(1152, 460/b, -461/a pages).

A ghazal with a recurring line of "Bilmadim" (I don't know) was published as a 7-couplet poem. In the medical collection, however, it consisted of 9 couplets. The remaining couplets appeared in the 8th and 9th positions in the collection.

Ixtiyor etdim oning ishqini so'ngra, ey ko'ngul,

Jong'a chekmak dardini dushvor ekandur bilmadim.

Bu kecha Feruzni shirin labidan aylagan,

Shodkom ul la'li shakar bor ekandur bilmadim (1152, 404/b pages).

In the published version, a ghazal that starts with the line "Bir dam aylab holima lutf oshkor, ey gulbadan" was given 10 couplets. In the collection "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy", the same ghazal consisted of 11 couplets. The remaining couplet is as follows:

Husni davronin g'animat anglab et ko'nglumni shod

Ne uchunkim bexazon ermas bisyor, ey gulbadan (1152, 588a/b pages).

In the collection, the remaining couplet is placed in the ninth position. The ghazal that begins with the line “Manga, ey dilrabo, buncha itob etmak nedur, bilmon” in the collection consisted of 7 couplets, but in the publication, it was reduced to 6 couplets. The couplet that was excluded from the publication was moved to the second position in the collection and consists of two couplets:

*Giriftoring erurlar jonu dil band etgali olin,
Musalsal kokilingni behitob etmak nedur bilmon.*

(1152, 576/b, 577/a pages).

The ghazal that starts with the line “Manga rahm aylab ul shirinzabon ohista-ohista” was given 10 couplets in the published version. In the collection, however, the same ghazal consisted of 11 couplets. The remaining couplet is as follows:

Agar istarsen o ‘pmaklikni eng jonfizo la’lin,

Qucharsan quch, belim eng miyon ohista-ohista (1152, 676/a pages).

The remaining couplet was moved to the eighth position in the collection:

A ghazal that starts with the line - “Na xush bo‘lg‘ay kishi bir gulshan ichra dilbari birla” was reduced to 5 couplets in the published version, even though it originally had 7 couplets. The remaining couplets appeared in the fourth and fifth positions in the collection. They are:

Solib bo ‘ynig‘a qo ‘l gohi o ‘pub siymin saqoqidin

Hayoti toza topsaki lab jon parvari birla.

Quchib nozik belidin cheksa jon ichra ulfati yanglig‘

Qur‘on etgay nechukkim mehranvar mushtariy birla (1152, 743/a-page).

These remaining couplets that were not published have important significance in creating the critical and scientific text of Feruz’s poetry.

2. Missing ghazals. Many of Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz II’s poems were published by G. Ismoilova in the works “Ne bo‘ldi yorim kelmadi” (1991) and “Elga shoh-u ishqqa qul” (1994). However, in these collections, there were also many of

the poet's unpublished works that were brought to attention. So, as a result of our previous work, focusing on the ghazals of Feruz that were published in various sources, we aimed to study the collection "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy", compiled by Tabibiy. As a result, we discovered three ghazals that were not included in the collections "Ne bo'ldi yorim kelmadi" and "Elga shoh-u ishqqa qul". Below, we are providing the **matla'** (first couplet) and **maqta'** (last couplet) for these ghazals:

"Ul yigit" radifli ghazal

*Shukr etib sarkash sumandin qilsa javlon ul yigit,
Qilg 'usidir dahr elin husniga hayron ul yigit.*

*Vaslig 'a yo 'l bermayin hijronida Feruzning
Ko 'nglini mag 'zun qilib, ko 'zini giryon ul yigit (1152. 145a/b-page).*

"Ul yigit" radifli ghazal

*Kelibon bazmim aro bir kecha pinhon ul yigit
Lutf etib qildi labidin bo 'sa ehson ul yigit.*

*Yo 'lida qilsam agar devonalig ' Feruzdek,
Man sori boqib labin qilmasmu xandon ul yigit (1152. 153b-page).*

"Ul o'g'ul" radif ghazal

*Aylabon ruxsorig 'a zulfin parishon ul o 'g 'ul,
Orazi mehrin ko 'zumdin qildi pinhon ul o 'g 'ul.*

*May ichib, may tobidin gulrang aylab orazin,
Ayladi Feruzni husniga hayron ul o 'g 'ul (1152. 496a/b-page).*

These ghazals written in the traditional style with the titles "Ul Yigit" (2 of them) and "Ul Og'ul" are exemplary of Feruz's devotion to Navoi.

Nowadays, there is a need to study Muhammad Rahimxon Feruz's creative work based on the original sources, and to compile his unpublished poems from various notebooks and collections to announce in current publications.

These are the main points covered in this article:

1. It has been clarified that the arrangement of Feruz's ghazals in "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy" has been mistakenly published in previous editions.
2. It has been pointed out that Feruz's ghazals titled "Ul o'g'ul" and two other ghazals under the title "Ul yigit" (42 verses) have not been published in current publications.

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